

Human Resurrection Project

Can science resurrect the dead using information extracted from DNA?

Abstract

DNA and information combined with science and biotechnology. Can we reverse death?

The process

In a science fiction movie set in the 23rd century, scientists were able to “recreate” a deceased human being, using only the information extracted from their DNA. With that information at their disposal, they were able to bring him back to life using biotechnology. The process is pure science-fiction and the idea of bringing back to life a deceased person can only be considered as something utopian. The question remains: can we ever resurrect the dead?

Conclusion

Although the process is a science fiction fantasy, the tendency of these ideas getting fulfilled is very likely with the advances of science and biotechnology. Using this logic, the question is not if it’s going to happen, but is when?

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